

Complexes of Some Bivalent Metals with Substituted Triazole and Thiadiazole Derivatives

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The complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with 3,5-dicarboxymethylthio-4-amino-4, 1,2-triazole and 2,5-dicarboxymethylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazole of the general formula ML_nH_2O ($n=1, 2$ or 3) have been prepared and characterised by UV, IR and magnetic susceptibility measurement. The spectral parameter $10Dq$, B and β of the octahedral complexes of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) have been calculated.

THE complex compounds of 4-amino-3, 5-dimercapto-1, 2, 4-triazole and 2, 5-dimercapto-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole have been reported earlier from this laboratory¹ and by other workers²⁻⁴. 3, 5-Dicarboxymethylthio-4-amino-4, 1, 2-triazole (H_2dtat) and 2, 5-dicarboxymethylthio-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole (H_2dtth) are multidentate ligands possessing nitrogen, sulphur and carboxylic oxygens as potent donor

sites. The complexing behaviour of these ligands does not appear to be reported in literature hitherto. In present communication we are reporting the complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with these ligands.

Experimental

All chemicals and solvents used were either E. Merck extra pure or BDH (A.R.) quality and used without further purification. The ligand was prepared as described elsewhere⁵.

Preparation of complexes: ML_nH_2O ($M=Mn^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ; $LH=H_2dtat$ and H_2dtth and $n=1, 2$ or 3).

Hydrated metal acetate (0.01 mole dissolved in 30-40 ml of methanol) were mixed to a hot methanolic solution of ligand (0.01 mole) and refluxed on a steam bath for about 15 minutes. The complexes either separated out immediately or on cooling the refluxate at room temperature. The products were washed with methanol and ether and dried in air. The colour, analytical results and magnetic moment values of the complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE-1

Compounds	Colour	% of Metal		% of Nitrogen		% of Carbon		% of Hydrogen		μ_{eff} (BM)
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
$[Ni(dtat)(H_2O)_2]H_2O$	Light blue	15.43	15.65	14.78	14.93	19.19	19.20	1.61	1.60	3.54
$[Ni(dtth)(H_2O)_2]H_2O$	Light blue	15.45	15.59	7.29	7.43	19.13	19.11	1.06	1.06	3.32
$[Co(dtat)(H_2O)_2]H_2O$	Pink	15.69	15.73	14.85	14.93	19.20	19.19	1.62	1.60	5.12
$[Co(dtth)(H_2O)_2]H_2O$	Pink	15.40	15.65	7.58	7.43	19.15	19.10	1.05	1.06	4.85
$[Mn(dtat)(H_2O)_2]H_2O$	Pinkish white	14.97	14.79	14.98	15.09	19.80	19.85	1.62	1.61	6.08
$[Mn(dtth)(H_2O)]$	Pinkish white	16.37	16.30	8.32	8.31	21.39	21.37	1.20	1.18	5.84
$[Cu(dtat)].2H_2O$	Green	17.45	17.55	15.58	15.49	19.95	19.90	1.68	1.66	1.92
$[Cu(dtth)].2H_2O$	Green	17.36	17.46	7.79	7.70	19.75	19.81	1.15	1.10	1.82
$[Cd(dtat)].2H_2O$	White	27.80	27.78	13.58	13.63	17.60	17.53	1.43	1.40	Dia.
$[Cd(dtth)].2H_2O$	White	27.57	27.67	6.89	6.79	17.50	17.46	1.00	0.96	Dia.
$[Zn(dtat)].H_2O$	White	19.03	18.91	16.21	16.20	20.91	20.83	1.75	1.73	Dia.
$[Zn(dtth)].2H_2O$	White	17.86	17.88	6.70	7.66	19.75	19.70	1.10	1.09	Dia.

Physical Measurements :

The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were determined by Gouy method⁶, reflectance spectra recorded on Hilger Watt UV spectrophotometer No.H-700 in the range of 350-1000 nm and IR spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 237 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

From the results of elemental analyses, it is found that H₂dtth and H₂dtat exhibit their dibasic behaviour and form neutral complexes of composition M(dtth).nH₂O and M(dtat). nH₂O (n=1, 2 or 3) with bivalent zinc, cadmium, cobalt, copper, nickel and manganese.

The hydrated complexes on heating at 120°, either remain unaffected or partially lose water molecules without appreciable change in colour. This indicates that the water molecules which are lost below 120° are probably lattice water but those are retained, are most likely the coordinated water. Thus, considering the usual coordination number 6 for Co²⁺, Mn²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺, it is presumed that H₂dtth is bonded as quadridentate ligand with Co²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺ in complexes M(dtth). nH₂O. In case of complexes M(dtat). nH₂O (M=Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Cu²⁺), the ligand is also quadridentate, forming bridges between two metal atoms.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra :

The room temperature magnetic moment values of the complexes of Ni²⁺ ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.09-3.19$ BM), Co²⁺ (4.85—5.12 BM) and Mn²⁺ (5.84—6.08 BM) are straight forward and fall in the range of high spin octahedral complexes of respective metal ions⁷.

Copper (II) complexes display magnetic moment values in the range of 1.82—1.92 BM, similar to magnetically dilute copper (II) complexes⁸. As expected, the zinc (II) and cadmium (II) complexes are diamagnetic.

The electronic reflectance spectra of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Mn²⁺ complexes do not exhibit electronic bands in the range 28500—10000 cm⁻¹. The medium to weak reflectance bands of complex [Ni(dtth)(H₂O)₂].H₂O and [Ni(dtat)(H₂O)₂].H₂O at 25000 and 15385—14705 cm⁻¹ are attributed to ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(F) transitions in octahedral ligand field. The values of 10Dq, B' and β (Table 2) calculated from the relation of ν₂ and ν₃ transitions^{9,10} indicate that ligand produces weak field around nickel (II) atom. The copper (II) complexes Cu(dtth).2H₂O and Cu(dtat).2H₂O display strong and asymmetric band in the region 15385—12195 cm⁻¹ assignable to combination of ²B_{1g}→²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g}→²E_g transition^{11,12} and another shoulder near 27027cm⁻¹ (probably charge transfer type). The medium and asymmetric band of Cu(dtth).2H₂O on the higher energy range 15385—12902 cm⁻¹ indicates a lower degree of distortion from octahedral environment in the complex. Both cobalt(II) complexes display two ligand field reflectance bands near 22000 sh and 19000 cm⁻¹ (strong) assignable to ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴T_{1g}→⁴A_{2g}(F) transition, though the latter transition is generally not observed in octahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹⁸. The second band has probably gained intensity due to tetragonal distortion of cobalt(II) ion. The value of 10Dq, B' and β (Table-II) computed from the relations of ν₂ and ν₃ transition of solid complexes fall in the range of octahedral environment of ligand atoms around cobalt(II) ions¹³.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS, THEIR PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS AND CRYSTAL FIELD PARAMETERS

Complexes	Band position (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment	10 Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B'(cm ⁻¹)	β	ν ₁ (cm ⁻¹)
[Co(dtat)(H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O	19230	⁴ T _{1g} — ⁴ A _{2g}	10247	967	0.99	8983
	22222	⁴ T _{1g} — ⁴ T _{1g} (P)				
[Co(dtth)(H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O	19607	⁴ T _{1g} — ⁴ A _{2g}	10690	923	0.95	8917
	21739	⁴ T _{1g} — ⁴ T _{1g} (P)				
[Ni(dtat)(H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O	15385	³ A _{2g} — ³ T _{1g} (F)	9456	788	0.75	9456
	25000	³ A _{2g} — ³ T _{1g} (P)				
[Ni(dtth)(H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O	14705	³ A _{2g} — ³ T _{1g} (F)	9163	833	0.79	9163
	25000	³ A _{2g} — ³ T _{1g} (P)				
[Cu(dtat)].2H ₂ O	13890-12195	² B _{1g} — ² B _{2g} ² E _g	-	-	-	-
	[Cu(dtth)].2H ₂ O	26666-15385-12902	C—T ² B _{1g} — ² B _{2g} ² E _g	-	-	-

IR spectra :

From the studies of a systematic shift in the IR spectral bands of 2, 5-dicarboxymethylthio-1, 3, 4-thiadiazol and 3, 5-dicarboxymethylthio-4-amino-1, 2, 4-triazole in their complexes, bonding of the ligand molecules has been suggested.

Free ligands display a number of bands in 3-3.5 μ region attributable to $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu_s(\text{CH}_2)$, $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_2)$ and $\nu(\text{OH})$ vibrations. Medium bands observed at 2720 and 2605 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of H_2dtat and 2700 and 2580 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of H_2dtth are attributed to H-bonded (COOH) group. These bands disappear in the IR spectra of metal complexes supporting the coordination of ligand by deprotonation of carboxylic OH.

The IR spectrum of H_2dtat displays strong bands at 3350 and 3210 cm^{-1} which are shifted to lower wave numbers in its complexes. These bands are assigned to NH asymmetric and symmetric vibration of NH_2 group. The shift of the $\nu(\text{NH})$ vibrations suggest the bonding of NH_2 group in H_2dtat complexes. The $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ vibration of H_2dtat and H_2dtth is observed as broad and very strong band at 1700 cm^{-1} (H_2dtat) and 1690—1730 cm^{-1} in case of H_2dtth ¹⁴. In complexes the $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ is shifted to lower frequencies and observed as broad band near 1590—1640 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ is observed at 1300—1305 cm^{-1} in free ligands which is shifted to higher frequencies in their complexes and observed at 1360—1400 cm^{-1} . From the shift in $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ vibration, it is inferred that both carboxyl oxygen is involved in bonding¹⁵⁻¹⁷. It appears that one of carboxylic oxygen is bonded to water molecules present in the complexes while the second one is bonded to metal atoms. The $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ band of H_2dtat is observed at 1640 cm^{-1} but in complexes it is leaved in strong $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ vibration.

In the region 1450—750 cm^{-1} free ligands display a number of bands attributable to $\delta(\text{OH})$ and CH_2 deformation, $\nu(\text{C—N})$, $\nu(\text{C—C})$ CH_2 wagging, CH_2 rocking, $\nu(\text{C—O})$ and $\nu(\text{C=S})$ vibrations. These vibrations are not well resolved and sharp in the complexes. The IR spectra of H_2dtth exhibits

a medium band at 750 cm^{-1} which is shifted to lower frequency and observed near $700 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting that thiosulphur of H_2dtth are involved in coordination. In case of uncoordinated H_2dtat , a number of weak bands could be observed in the region 800—700 cm^{-1} and therefore no definite position of $\nu(\text{C—S})$ band either in free ligand or its complexes could be ascertained. But from analogy the coordination of ether sulphurs may also be suggested in its complexes.

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